

TWINNING MATTERS

No small roles, just shared impact

Twinning creates structured, 3-year small consortium partnerships between Widening institutions and excellence centres. It builds sustainable capacity in research, project management, open science, and proposal design – raising success rates and visibility in EU programmes.

WHAT WORKS

Skills & Management

Increased professional competence through mentoring, exchanges, and targeted training.

Research Excellence

Increased publication output & proposal quality

Institutional Growth

New RMA offices, data stewardship, open science policies

Collaboration

Long-term partnership with excellence institutions

Earth
Bridge

TWINVECTOR

HYBRID
NEURO

gemstone

REMODEL

Remote
Ethnography
X U A R

SMART4ENV

BAANG

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